

Tritium Production Analysis of LiCl-KCl Coolant Salt in the Primary Heat Exchanger of a Chloride Salt-Based Molten Salt Reactor

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ABSTRACT

Despite the inherent safety and high-efficiency characteristics of Molten Salt Reactors (MSRs), high-temperature operation increases the risk of tritium (T) permeation through metal structures and subsequent environmental release. This study quantitatively assessed the tritium generation rate in the LiCl-KCl coolant salt within the out-of-core Primary Heat Exchanger (PHX) of a Li-free chloride-salt (NaCl-KCl-UCl₃) Fast-Spectrum MSR (100 MWt). The analysis utilized the SCALE 6.3.1 code system. The design strategy involves eliminating the primary source of T generation (Li) from the primary fuel salt and placing the PHX in a shielded, out-of-core location. The analysis yielded a tritium generation rate of 7.81×10^{-5} Ci/MWt/d. This value is more than four orders of magnitude lower than the normalized benchmark rate for conventional FLiBe MSRs (approx. 1.07 Ci/MWt/d). This finding validates the chloride-salt and out-of-core PHX placement strategy as an innovative solution for mitigating the tritium management challenge, thereby providing essential data for the radiological safety assessment and source term analysis of chloride salt-based MSR systems.

Keywords: Molten Salt Reactors, Tritium, SCALE, Chloride-based salt, Fast Spectrum

1. INTRODUCTION

The Molten Salt Reactor (MSR) has emerged as one of the most promising next-generation reactor technologies due to its inherent safety mechanisms, high thermal efficiency through high-temperature operation ($> 600^{\circ}\text{C}$), and multi-purpose capabilities (e.g., hydrogen production, process heat, and power generation). The MSR design under development in this study utilizes a chloride salt-based fuel salt (NaCl-KCl-UCl₃), which does not serve as an effective neutron moderator, thus exhibiting the characteristics of a Fast-Spectrum MSR. Conventional MSR research, primarily focused on fluoride-based salts (e.g., FLiBe), has concentrated on tritium generation within the core. These designs typically use a graphite moderator, operating in a thermal neutron spectrum, which significantly amplifies the ${}^6\text{Li}(n, \alpha){}^3\text{H}$ reaction. However, the high operating temperature (approximately 650°C) of MSRs significantly accelerates the risk of tritium permeation through metallic structures and subsequent release into the environment. Since the chloride salt-based MSR primary loop contains no lithium, the amount of tritium generated in the primary system can be drastically reduced. This study aims to quantitatively assess the tritium generation rate in the chloride salt-based and fast spectrum MSR system using the SCALE 6.3.1 computer code system [1] and to subsequently discuss effective tritium management strategies for this advanced reactor design by comparing the generation rates across major MSR types normalized by thermal power.

2. Reactor and Primary Heat Exchanger Geometric Structure and Material Specifications

The reactor model employed in this study has a 100 MW thermal output and utilizes a NaCl-KCl-UCl₃ salt mixture at a composition of 42.9-20.3-36.8 mol% as the primary fuel salt.

The selected coolant salt is the eutectic LiCl-KCl composition (40.8-59.2 mol%). The Li isotope in the coolant salt uses natural abundance (Li-6: 7.5%; Li-7: 92.5%). LiCl-KCl coolant salt was chosen for the following reasons: its low eutectic melting point of 352°C mitigates the potential for localized freezing in downstream systems, such as the steam generator. Furthermore, its low viscosity and high thermal conductivity ensure excellent heat transfer performance.

The reactor core features a cylindrical structure with a 76 cm radius, capped by hemispherical heads at the top and bottom. This core is radially enveloped by an 80 cm-thick MgO reflector, which is further contained within an SS-316 (Stainless Steel 316) reactor vessel. The shell-and-tube type PHX system is positioned 10 cm radially outward from the reactor vessel, with one unit situated on the left and one on the right. This heat exchanger is encased in a 5 cm thick SS-316 layer. Heat exchange is performed between the hot fuel salt, which flows from the reactor outlet, and the coolant salt (LiCl-KCl) circulating through 2,339 SS-316 tubes. Each tube has a diameter of 0.2 cm and a height of 400 cm. The detailed geometric configurations of the reactor and the heat exchanger are presented in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

Figure 1. Configuration of Chloride salt-based MSR

Figure 2. Horizontal Cut of Primary Heat exchanger

3. Tritium Generation Evaluation

3.1. Tritium Generation Mechanism in Molten Salt Reactors

The major reaction contributing to tritium generation is the interaction of lithium isotopes with neutrons, which is far more dominant than tritium originating from fission products. The most significant generation pathway is the ${}^6\text{Li}(n, \alpha){}^3\text{H}$ reaction, where ${}^6\text{Li}$ captures a thermal neutron. This reaction possesses a very large thermal neutron capture cross-section of 940 barns (see Figure 3) [2], making ${}^6\text{Li}$ the overwhelmingly dominant source of tritium, even if present in trace amounts. Additionally, ${}^9\text{Be}$ has a reaction pathway that continuously produces ${}^6\text{Li}$ by absorbing a neutron. This is the fundamental reason why fluoride-salt-based FLiBe MSR systems exhibit high tritium generation rates. Consequently, MSRs utilizing Li-containing fuel salts must enrich ${}^7\text{Li}$ to over 99.99% to prevent excessive tritium generation.

Figure 3. Cross Section for Tritium Production Reaction by ${}^6\text{Li}(n, \alpha){}^3\text{H}$

3.2. Quantitative Comparison of Tritium Generation Rate by Major MSR Types

3.2.1. MSRE [3]

The Molten-Salt Reactor Experiment (MSRE), built and operated by Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL) in the 1960s to demonstrate the feasibility of a liquid fluoride nuclear fuel system, operated at a thermal power of 7.5 MWt. As a graphite-moderated reactor, it operated in a thermal neutron spectrum. The calculated tritium generation rate for MSRE using the LiF-BeF₂-ZrF₄-UF₄ (65-29.1-5-0.9 mol%) salt- utilizing lithium enriched to 99.99% in ⁷Li -varied based on the fuel used during operation:

- ✓ U-235 Operation (based on 7.34 MWt): The total generation was calculated to be 31.7 Ci/day, showing that the Li-6 reaction (28.3 Ci/day) was the overwhelming primary source (about 89%).
- ✓ U-233 Operation (based on 7.34 MWt): The total generation was calculated to be 56.4 Ci/day.

Normalizing the total generation rate for U-235 operation (31.7 Ci/day) by thermal power (7.34 MWt) yields approximately 4.3 Ci/MWt/d.

3.2.2. MSBR [4]

The evaluation results for the 1000 MW(e) Molten Salt Breeder Reactor (MSBR) reference design, performed by ORNL in the 1970s, are used as a benchmark for MSR tritium management. This design also utilizes a graphite moderator, resulting in a thermal neutron spectrum. Assuming 2,250 MWt thermal power, the calculated steady-state total tritium generation rate was 2,420 Ci/day. Normalizing this by thermal power: (Calculation: 2,420 Ci/day / 2250 MWt \approx 1.07 Ci/MWt/d). This generation rate of \sim 1.07 Ci/MWt/d is typical when using highly enriched (99.99%+ ⁷Li) FLiBe salt, where the ⁶Li and ⁷Li contributions are approximately 50% each.

3.2.3. TMSR [5]

The Thorium Molten Salt Reactor (TMSR) design developed in China reports significantly different generation rates compared to the aforementioned FLiBe-based designs. TMSR designs are graphite-moderated, operating in a thermal neutron spectrum. To effectively manage tritium production, these designs typically utilize FLiBe salt with ⁷Li enrichment levels ranging from 99.95% to 99.995%. According to reports on the TMSR design, the low-power TMSR (30 MWt) generates approximately 5.00×10^{15} Bq of tritium annually. In comparison, a larger commercial scale TMSR(2,250 MWt) is estimated to produce 3.75×10^{17} Bq of tritium per year. Normalizing the commercial scale TMSR data to Ci/MWt/d yields 12.30 Ci/MWt/d.

3.2.4. MSR used in this study

The 100 MWt chloride salt-based MSR under development in this study fundamentally differentiates itself from conventional fluoride-salt MSRs by adopting NaCl-KCl-UCl₃ as the fuel salt and eliminating the use of a graphite moderator. Considering that Li is the overwhelmingly major source of tritium generation, the amount of tritium generated inside the reactor can be significantly lower if the fuel salt does not contain Li.

This design pursues a fast-spectrum and uses an MgO reflector, and the Li-containing coolant salt (LiCl-KCl) is only present in the Primary Heat Exchanger (PHX), located outside the primary loop. Therefore, tritium generation predominantly occurs in the secondary loop coolant salt, not the primary fuel salt, and is determined by the local neutron irradiation at the PHX. This irradiation accounts for both leakage neutrons from the core and delayed neutrons emitted from the fuel salt circulating through the PHX.

The tritium generation in the coolant salt was calculated following these steps.

The first step is to establish the neutron flux field under the nominal operating state of the MSR core. The CSAS (Criticality Safety Analysis Sequence) within SCALE 6.3.1 uses the KENO-VI Monte Carlo code to calculate the fission distribution within the core.

The tritium generation within the PHX was evaluated by tallying the entire PHX volume, thereby accounting for all local nuclear reactions occurring within that region. While this approach captures the total neutron flux environment in the PHX. It is acknowledged that the current modeling approach using SCALE 6.3.1 is not sufficient to fully account for the advection of fuel salt and the subsequent physical transport of delayed neutron

precursors from the core to the PHX. However, given the shielded out-of-core location, the current results serve as a robust baseline for evaluating the tritium source term in the secondary loop coolant. High-resolution mesh tallies are used in the core calculation to obtain the spatial and energetic distribution of fission neutrons. This flux map becomes the input for the subsequent MAVRIC calculation.

The MAVRIC sequence is designed for radiation shielding and dose analysis, combining a Monte Carlo transport code (Monaco or Shift) with automated variance reduction methods.

MAVRIC converts the fission distribution calculated in the first step into a source term to evaluate the tritium generation rate occurring inside the PHX.

According to the calculated results, the amount of tritium generated in the LiCl-KCl coolant salt of the PHX at 100 MWt output is 0.318 mCi/day. Normalizing this value by thermal power yields 3.18×10^{-6} Ci/MWt/d. This figure is remarkably low compared to fluoride-salt-based MSR. This demonstrates that the design strategy utilizing a Li-free chloride salt-based fuel and a fast-neutron spectrum, combined with the out-of-core location of the Li-containing coolant, can innovatively mitigate the tritium generation issue. Table 1 compares the normalized thermal power-based tritium generation rates for major MSR types.

Table 1. Comparison of Tritium Generation Rates by MSR Type

Reactor Type	Thermal Power (MWt)	Tritium Generation (Ci/day)	Normalized Rate (Ci/MWt/d)	Neutron Spectrum
This Study	100	3.18×10^{-4}	3.18×10^{-6}	Fast
MSBR	2,250	2,420	1.07	Thermal
MSRE (U-235)	7.34	31.7	4.3	Thermal
TMSR (Commercial)	2,250	27,750	12.3	Thermal

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study quantitatively assessed the tritium generation rate within the Primary Heat Exchanger (PHX), which utilizes a lithium-containing coolant salt, as part of the safety evaluation for a chloride salt-based Fast-Spectrum MSR. The SCALE 6.3.1 code system was employed to perform the analysis.

As a key finding, the tritium generation rate in the PHX coolant salt at 100 MWt output was determined to be 3.18×10^{-6} Ci/MWt/d. This figure represents a reduction of more than 10^6 times compared to the normalized generation rates of conventional FLiBe-based MSRs (e.g., the MSBR benchmark of ~ 1.07 Ci/MWt/d).

This remarkably low generation rate validates the success of two critical design strategies. First, the use of Li-free NaCl-KCl-UCl₃ chloride salt as the primary fuel fundamentally eliminated the main source of tritium generation from the reactor core itself. Second, by placing the Li-containing coolant system (PHX) outside the core and shielding it with the MgO reflector, the influence of thermal neutron flux—the primary driver of the Li-6 reaction—was minimized, further reinforced by the overall fast-neutron spectrum of the core itself, which inherently lowers the Li-6 reaction cross-section.

In conclusion, this chloride salt-based MSR design demonstrates the potential to innovatively mitigate the severe issue of tritium management, marking a significant step toward overcoming a major safety barrier for MSR

commercialization. This dramatic reduction offers design flexibility by minimizing the reliance on complex and expensive tritium capture and removal systems.

Future work will focus on performing tritium permeation and transport analyses, incorporating the material-specific transport properties and temperature gradients within the PHX structure, to comprehensively assess the final release risk to the environment.

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